

From the Umbrella into the Forest

A Journey through Recent Visual Metaphors of Open Science

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Abstract

This study presents an overview of the visual metaphors which have been employed by Open Science (OS) communities to depict and define the concept over the last ten years. The concise overview presented here is founded on the methodological premise that metaphorical language is particularly fruitful in science, as it holds an expansive and heuristic power (Marras, 2013). Section 1 analyses the categorisation of these figures into human-made artifacts, such as the ‘umbrella’ (an overarching term for openness) and the ‘wheel’ (a cyclical engine of knowledge). Section 2 is dedicated to conceptual structures such as the hierarchical ‘taxonomy’ and the decentralised ‘graph’. A significant transition is identified with natural organisms, namely the ‘mushroom’ and the ‘tree’, which are analysed in section 3. Section 4 introduces the ‘forest’ of OS metaphor, which offers a synthesis capable of incorporating the strengths of the previous images. The power of the forest metaphor lies both in its ability to make real tensions visible, forcing us to confront the gap between the model and our practices, and in its capacity to define a model of OS grounded in ecological intelligence. The forest thus serves as a descriptive model, forcing us to confront the real disparities in our knowledge ecosystems, but it also helps us to define a vision, a philosophical framework based on the vision of ecological intelligence.

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Introduction

This study presents a comprehensive overview of the visual metaphors - the umbrella, the wheel, the taxonomy, the tree, the mushroom, and the graph - which have been employed by Open Science (OS) communities to depict and define the concept over the last ten years. The decision to analyse the imagery of OS arose from a reflection prompted by studies on metaphors as connecting figures in the process through which a concept is understood and structured using the terms of another concept (Marras 2017:6). The subsequent concise overview is founded on the methodological premise that metaphorical language is particularly fruitful in science, as it has an expansive and heuristic power (Marras, 2013).

The following investigation will therefore examine these metaphors, through which it is possible to map the meaning of OS from one domain of knowledge - the figurative - to another reflecting the practices and imagery of specific cultures, by integrating images, linguistic expressions and conceptual mappings. The images of the umbrella, the wheel, the taxonomy, the graph, the mushroom and the tree, are employed as metaphors for OS, thereby conveying the relevant concepts and broadening the scope of the topic. Furthermore, they enable the definition of imaginaries that offer a representation of the research cultures that produced and represented them. As the comprehension of the values, priorities and cultural assumptions of a developing movement is contingent upon an understanding of their reading, these metaphors are therefore analysed as instruments which, by incorporating both linguistic expressions and conceptual mappings, serve to enrich the meaning and context of OS movements and practices.

1. Human-made Artifacts: the Umbrella and the Wheel

In their 2013 essay, Fecher and Friesike propose a definition of OS as a general term, or, as the authors themselves suggest, as an ‘umbrella term’. In this way OS is defined as a concept that encompasses a multitude of related ideas or entities, grouped under a general label in order to facilitate their identification and understanding. The overarching term encapsulates a series of assumptions concerning the future of knowledge production and dissemination, unified by the notion that science necessitates enhanced openness. However, it should be noted that the term ‘openness’ can refer to different aspects: the process of knowledge creation, its outcomes, or its relationship with society. The involvement of numerous actors in the process of scientific creation results in the contribution of a variety of perspectives. The authors identify five schools of thought, depending on the main premise on which they are based and the meaning of openness on which the relevant actors (researchers, policy makers, software developers, publishers and the general public) focus. The umbrella image is arguably derived from this definition, constituting the initial step in our examination of recent visual representations of OS.

The metaphor of the umbrella is intricately linked to several further meanings. Indeed, it is a man-made artifact created to serve a purpose and meet a specific need: namely, to provide shelter for what lies beneath from inclement weather conditions. The metaphor of the umbrella, therefore, as well as representing multiple elements under a single canopy, conveys the idea of utility, and of a human creation in response to a specific need. The internet is replete with images that translate this meaning into graphic form in various ways and with different content.

Fig. 1 - Four umbrellas of Open Science: (a) Source: Public & Science Sweden; (b) Champieux 2019; (c) Fiocruz 2019; (d) Mendéz 2016.

The images in figure 1 show that what lies beneath a common denominator (the OS umbrellas) varies significantly.

Figure 1a is taken from the website of Public & Science Sweden (Vetenskap & Allmänhet), a Swedish non-profit organisation dedicated to promoting dialogue and the openness of knowledge. As illustrated, the label 'open science' is situated at the uppermost point, thereby encompassing the umbrella and the elements to which it pertains. These elements, which comprise three components or practices ('open access', 'public engagement' and 'open data'), are emphasised and connected by arrows, thus conveying the notion of interaction between them. It is evident that ancillary components (depicted on a reduced scale) serve to enhance the overarching framework of practices. It is also clear that, in addition to a discernible hierarchy among the components of OS, considerable emphasis is placed on the concept of 'Public Engagement' and its associated practices, including 'Co-creation', 'Open Participation', 'Citizen Science' and 'Public Involvement'. The image under consideration here highlights how components are scaled and linked to a specific organisational priority, namely Public Engagement. This reflects the Citizen Science and science communication activities of the Swedish organisation, which include the organisation of events such as the European Researchers' Night.

Figure 1b was used by EOOSC-hub, a project funded by the European Union under Horizon 2020, whose main aim was to provide simplified and integrated access to a wide range of digital resources, software and

services for data-driven research¹. In the image, the label ‘open science’ is placed on the umbrella, most of which are digital resources (including ‘open access’, ‘open educational resources’, ‘open source’, ‘open data’) and a single label brings together the three values of ‘equity, diversity and inclusion’ found in the UNESCO Recommendation (2021). Here, the focus is on the accessibility of results in a context defined by general values.

Figure 1c is used by the Brazilian SciELO project (an acronym for Biblioteca Científica Electrónica en Línea), a wide-ranging digital library throughout South America founded in 1998 that serves as a platform for the publication of scientific journals under an Open Access model and whose contents are freely and fully accessible. In the image - presented with the following caption: ‘An umbrella encompassing independent practices has become the most popular among Open Science concept imagery’ - , the eight components of OS are all placed on the same level and treated equally, and include Open Access to a variety of resources (scientific literature, data, software, laboratory notes, educational resources) as well as practices that define the openness of the processes of creation, evaluation and dissemination of these resources (‘citizen science’, ‘open peer review’ and ‘scientific social media’).

Figure 1d was created by Eva Méndez (2016), professor at the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M), and a leading expert and advocate for OS and open knowledge who played a significant role in shaping European open science policies². Unlike the other umbrellas, Méndez presents a hand-drawn illustration. Furthermore, in this illustration the umbrella is placed within an adverse external context (it has rain falling on it). Beneath the umbrella and sheltered from the rain are six components: alongside the openness of scientific literature, data and software, and citizen science, Méndez enriches the metaphor introducing the openness of processes (‘open research’, ‘open methodologies’, ‘open scientific workflows’). Moreover, three additional elements complement the base of the umbrella: ‘research integrity’, ‘research infrastructure’ and ‘altmetrics’, the first two of which are not present in other representations.

Looking at the four images confirms that there is no single definition of OS, but also allows us to understand and interpret the perspectives of the various communities in question, revealing their practices, principles and values.

In 2015, Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman initiated a survey with the objective of mapping the tools utilised by researchers in their research activities³. The survey is predicated on the assumption that the evolving landscape is primarily reflected in changes in the tools researchers use in their day-to-day work, and that a snapshot of these tools can help to outline the practices of OS. In their study on innovations in

¹ The EOSC-Hub project ran from January 2018 to December 2020 and involved 100 partners from 53 countries.

² Méndez chaired the EU Open Science Policy Platform (2018–2020), and served on the Steering Board of CoARA (2022-2024). See her ORCID profile here: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5337-4722>.

³ The distribution of the questionnaires encompassed seven languages, and the two Dutch librarians were responsible for the reception and analysis of 20,663 responses. The languages encompassed English, Spanish, French, Chinese, Russian, Japanese and Arabic. The majority of respondents (72%) were academic and scientific staff: The demographic composition of the sample was as follows: 41.7% of the participants held professorial positions, 31% were classified as early-career researchers (comprising PhD and post-doctoral students), and 8.5% were graduates. The responses received from the library sector, publishing industry and government are discussed in the following section.

academic communication, Kramer and Bosman comprehensively analyse and interpret the behaviours and motivations of scientists, highlighting the influence of factors such as field, country and position. The objective of this study is to address the question of how these innovations might change workflows and practices and contribute to a more open science, starting from an analysis of researchers' immediate needs.

The raw data and results of the aggregated analyses are available in a variety of open formats and have been published on the 'Innovations in Scholarly Communication' project website⁴. Kramer and Bosman thus provide a snapshot of academic communication practices and, more generally, of scientific research within a constantly evolving landscape, in which new tools are continually being developed by researchers themselves, small start-ups or large companies. The final results encompass over 600 innovations, associated with sixty-six research practices.

The structure of the questionnaire is delineated by a six-stage workflow, encompassing the following phases: preparation, discovery, analysis, writing, publication, dissemination and impact, and evaluation (cf. Figure 2a). It is evident that specific practices are associated with each phase. For instance, the 'discovery' phase encompasses bibliographic research, searching for datasets or code, accessing sources, reading and annotating, as well as receiving notifications or reading recommendations. Conversely, the 'writing' stage comprises activities such as writing text or code, citing sources and translation, as illustrated in Figure 2b.

Fig. 2 - (a) The phases of scientific research; (b) Examples of activities or practices relating to the various phases; (c) The interactions between the various phases (Kramer, Bosman. 2017a: 10–12); (d) The Open Science Wheel and its activities or practices, organised by phase (Kramer, Bosman. 2017).

⁴ The project website can be accessed via the following link: <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>.

As illustrated in Figure 2c, the constituent phases of this process have a cyclical iterative nature. This transition from parts to whole, and vice versa, is evident in the sequence of events, including rounds of grant/project writing, multiple iterations during the discovery phase, experiments, drafting, rewriting, submission and resubmission. Finally, Figure 2d presents the results of the mapping of OS practices through another image of a human-made artifact, the 'Open Science Wheel', which encompasses sixty-six different practices⁵.

The practices mapped by the wheel are varied, ranging from making conflicts of interest transparent or pre-registering studies in a preparatory phase, to recording steps and inputs or sharing reading activities in order to make them usable as information filters (during the discovery phase); from open sharing of online notebooks (in the analysis phase) to coding and writing collaboratively, and translating research objects in world languages (during the writing activity); from the recognition of different roles in the production of a scientific result (in the publication phase) to the archiving and sharing of presentations and using a narrative approach to assess research (respectively, in the outreach and assessment phases). It goes without saying that not everyone does everything, and that the image provides us with a snapshot of the practices in use at a specific point in time. As such, the image has a descriptive function. As Kramer and Bosman (2017b) also acknowledge, the definition of OS is variable depending on the priorities of individual researchers or organisations. This diversity is indicative of the divergent choices made by researchers, which are inextricably contextual and influenced by their respective disciplines, as well as by geographical, institutional, economic and social factors.

As a metaphor, the wheel establishes an equivalence between OS and Open Research, thereby elevating OS from a mere collection of practices to a fundamental engine of knowledge creation. Moreover, by symbolising OS as a cyclical process between the open research phases (see Fig. 2c) the wheel evokes the hermeneutic circle, i.e. “a metaphor for the procedure of transforming one's understanding of the part and the whole through iterative recontextualization”⁶, thereby implying a vision of OS as a continuous, infinite process.

Furthermore, the metaphor emphasises the reuse of existing knowledge and continuous interpretation as an open-ended process. Indeed, while the image of the wheel refers to a human-made artifact, it is also one of humanity's most significant inventions, and the metaphor carries two further meanings: firstly, it elevates OS from a mere collection of practices to a fundamental process, a driving force for the production of knowledge. Secondly, it underscores a fundamental tenet of OS, namely the significance of reusing pre-existing knowledge, a principle that is encapsulated by the adage, 'don't reinvent the wheel'. The image below, frequently cited in discussions pertaining to OS, serves to underscore the aforementioned implications.

⁵ The OS Wheel has been released under a Creative Commons BY licence, and is available in a vector format, thus enabling users to explore it (Kramer, Bosman, 2017).

⁶ Hermeneutical circle, Wikipedia entry: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hermeneutic_circle.

Fig. 3 - In the cartoon, a group of primitive men are depicted as engaged in the laborious task of transporting a load of stones on a cart lacking wheels. A third man offers them a wheel, and they decline, saying, "No thanks! We are too busy". (Giglia, 2016).

2. Conceptual structures: the Taxonomy and the Graph

The Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research (FOSTER) project⁷, which was funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme from 2014 to 2016 and dedicated to the training of researchers in open science, developed a number of educational programmes based on a content classification diagram termed the 'open science taxonomy' (Pontika et al. 2015)⁸. FOSTER's OS taxonomy comprises six axes or branches: 'open access', 'open data', 'open and reproducible research', 'OS evaluation', 'OS policy', and 'OS tools'. Each of these includes sub-topics, totalling 43 entries.

⁷ The consortium has organised and supported a plethora of training events, with a total of over one hundred events taking place in twenty-eight countries, attended by a combined total of over six thousand people. The FOSTER portal, which is no longer directly accessible, collected and made available over one thousand eight hundred training resources. The project also offered e-learning courses, delivered in various formats, including online self-study and moderated classes. The European Commission has continued to allocate funding to open science training and continues to do so through calls for proposals under the current funding programme.

⁸ The taxonomy has undergone revisions and adjustments, as described, for example, in Silveira et al. (2023; 2023a).

Fig. 4 – The Open Science Taxonomy (Pontika et al. 2015).

Taxonomy is the system that organises the components of OS into a rigid structure conceived by humans. As a primary historical model for classifying human knowledge and operating as a flat hierarchical structure, the introduction of order and detail engenders a representation that is self-contained (finite) and partial. To illustrate this point, consider the absence of FAIR data (Wilkinson et al., 2016)⁹. As such, the FOSTER OS taxonomy offers a contextual description of OS.

The taxonomy under discussion here emerges from the combination of two overarching principles: the openness of content (which encompasses software and hardware, data, scientific literature in the broadest sense, and educational resources, assessments and quality evaluations) and the openness of processes (which means transparent methodology, early sharing, transparency of evaluation criteria, and obviously includes accessibility to all relevant documentation). These principles are embodied in the FOSTER definition of OS (Kramer et al. 2017)¹⁰, which emphasises the collaborative nature of research and the openness of results, data and underlying processes under conditions that allow for their reuse, redistribution and reproduction. The transparency of processes (including peer review) is instrumental in cultivating a scientific practice that is both ethical and responsible. Despite the fact that the taxonomy ultimately assumes a flat structure, it is predicated on the notion of cycles: of research; of academic communication; and of research data (Melero 2015: 11-20).

⁹ The FAIR principles were introduced in the same year that the taxonomy was conceived, which explains their absence.

¹⁰ “Open Science is the practice of science in such a way that others can collaborate and contribute, where research data, lab notes and other research processes are freely available, under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction of the research and its underlying data and methods.” Kramer, Bosman 2017 b.

A preparatory document for the UNESCO Recommendation presents an image of an OS graph, which has been widely circulated and is reproduced in Figure 5a. In the proposed image, the graph represents the relationships between the twelve components identified, which include the openness of scientific results (OA), data, educational resources, software and hardware, infrastructure and processes, as well as openness to the participation of actors outside the scientific system in the strict sense. The graph metaphor evokes a vision of OS understood not as a static collection or a linear process, but as a dynamic and decentralised network of relationships, and it strongly emphasises three fundamental objectives of the UNESCO Recommendation: making knowledge freely accessible, improving collaboration and information sharing, and opening up scientific processes to actors outside the traditional scientific community (UNESCO, 2021: 7), as shown in Figure 5b.

Fig. 5. (a) The components of OS (UNESCO 2020) and (b) their relationship with the definition in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO 2021:7)). The coloured circles have been added by the author and map the three dimensions indicated in the definition.

Like taxonomy, a graph is a conceptual structure, or more precisely, a mathematical one. As such, it is characterised by a set of vertices interconnected by edges. The field of graph theory was pioneered by Euler (1736), thus establishing its foundations in the discipline of network science. The Internet, the World Wide Web and the network of scientific citations are all graphs that share a common topology and obey common laws. (Barabasi 2002).

The information architecture diagram from Berners-Lee's initial proposal, which was submitted to the Director of CERN, provides a clear illustration of the concept of creating an information space based on objects and labelled relationships among them. This diagram also elucidates the underlying philosophical premise that "human knowledge is not a tree, but a network" (Berners-Lee, 2000).

Fig. 6 - The image is taken from “Information Management: A proposal”. It is the initial proposal for the World Wide Web submitted by Berners-Lee to CERN (Berners-Lee 1989–1990).

The graph carries strong philosophical and political significance. Its decentralised structure rejects the view of knowledge as a taxonomy; the strength of the graph, conversely, lies in the absence of a central authority and in the autonomy of its nodes, allowing users to navigate, verify, and govern the scientific process through transparent, trust-based connections.

Many documentation systems were designed for specific collections of information, and it could be assumed that the information contained in such systems had reached a certain standard of quality. However, the Web itself cannot impose a single concept of quality. Such concepts are highly subjective and change over time. To support this concept—that is, to enable users to make effective use of the Web even though it contains both useless and valuable information—the technology must provide powerful filtering tools which, by combining opinions and information from many sources, are entirely under the user’s control (Berners-Lee 2000).

The graph is a metaphor that rejects the top-down vision of knowledge as a centralised and hierarchical taxonomy. Conversely, it encapsulates a conceptualisation of OS as a continuous, open process wherein users (who are not exclusively scientists in the strict sense) have the autonomy to select their own paths, govern and verify methods and results, and thereby place their trust in it.

3. Natural organisms: The Mushroom and the Tree

A substantial conceptual transformation is evident with the introduction of the OS mushroom. Mushrooms fulfil a specific function within the ecosystem, facilitating the absorption of nutrients (particularly phosphorus and nitrogen) from the soil, whilst plants provide them with carbohydrates produced through photosynthesis. This exchange has been demonstrated to promote plant growth and health, as well as to improve soil structure and its capacity for water retention. Mushrooms are therefore considered to be an important symbol of collaboration within the ecosystem.

It is Méndez herself who instigates this fundamental transition, replacing an artifact with a natural living organism.

Fig. 7 - (a) Méndez 2016; (b) Eva Méndez's Open Science mushroom (Méndez, 2017).

In the transition from the umbrella to the mushroom, Méndez further enriches the image. The mushroom gills are representative of citizen science, whilst the stem is symbolic of standards and governance. The elements previously present in Méndez's own umbrella are joined by the LOD (Linked Open Data) label alongside open data, FLOSS (Free Libre Open Source) software, Text and Data Mining, and 'open design'.

Notably, the roots reshape the elements of research integrity, research infrastructure and alternative evaluation systems. These elements become foundational and essential, nourishing the visible parts of the organism. It is therefore relevant to emphasise that the roots of responsible research and innovation are established at this stage. Naturalistic fiction is employed here to assert that mushrooms possess roots. This way, Méndez posits that the mushroom functions not merely as a container for visible practices, but as an entity that facilitates a broader array of phenomena. The concept's strength lies in its introduction of the notion of a hidden, submerged system: a network of roots that can be considered analogous to the submerged mass of an iceberg. As Rafols et al. observe, the mushroom "consists of many visible (often digital) practical activities and also concerns, beneath its surface, many underlying institutional issues such as integrity, infrastructure and evaluation" (Rafols et al. 2024: 4). Moreover, for mushrooms' role in the ecosystem, this metaphor transitions OS to an active symbol of ecosystem collaboration. The mushroom

image has been extensively employed by OS communities, and a stylised version of it is reproduced in Figure 8.

Fig. 8 – The OS mushroom, based on Méndez (2017) (Fazekas-Paragh 2019).

This meaning is confirmed and reinforced by the image of the OS tree, a representation of which has been proposed by the Young European Research Universities Network (YERUN)¹¹.

¹¹ YERUN was founded in 2015 with a view to representing and promoting cooperation among young European research universities. In addition, it seeks to influence European Union policies in this regard.

Fig. 9 - Open Science Tree (YERUN 2018)

The image, also adopted by the European project OPUS (2020–2024)¹², depicts a slightly stylised tree with a dense canopy that conceals its branches and comprising eight macro-areas or principles: ‘collaboration’ (which includes participation and knowledge sharing), ‘visibility’ (under which greater impact falls), ‘open training’ (which encompasses FAIR data, open research data, open methodologies, support and leadership), ‘sharing of ideas’ (which includes accessibility, alternative publication models, open software) and ‘citizen science’ (with co-creation, reusability and transparency).

The other three macro-areas, ‘evaluation’, ‘incentives’ and ‘research integrity’, stem from the roots as in the mushroom model by Méndez (2017). The infrastructure, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), research evaluation and next-generation metrics also stem from the roots. These elements act as the tree sap, travelling from the roots through the trunk to the leaves.

The tree has in fact been the primary model used to represent the classification and organisation of knowledge, traditionally representing the unity and structure of science within a taxonomy of human knowledge (Marras 2013: 394–95). As Cristina Marras points out, beautiful tables were created to describe its internal classification, including the *Table de Mouchon* of 1780, which serves as the analytical index and a summary of Diderot and D’Alembert’s *Encyclopédie* (Marras 2013: 395). Nevertheless, Figure 9 emphasises the vitality of the natural organism, highlighting processes and interactions that carry nourishment from roots to outputs.

¹² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058471>.

Méndez herself uses the image of a tree (in this case, a Christmas tree) with a festive message sent to the community in 2022 in which research evaluation takes centre stage.

Fig. 10 - Open Science Christmas Tree (Méndez 2022)

At the tree's roots, the label 'reward system' replaces the more specific 'Altmetrics' and is highlighted. 'CoARA' (the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) appears on the tree trunk. The Christmas baubles feature the eight fundamental elements of this representation of OS: 'Open Access', 'Open Peer Review', 'Collaborative Science', 'Open Research', 'FAIR Data', 'Open Communication', 'Open Labs' and 'Open Citations'. These elements are linked by tinsels representing the various forms of science's openness to active public participation ('citizen science', 'Science 4all', 'Public engagement', 'Science with and for society'). The entire structure leads to the top of the Christmas tree, the star, which represents 'better science', i.e. high quality scientific knowledge. Here too, the tree metaphor establishes relationships and interactions between principles, values, processes and practices. It also embodies the idea of a big change.

The tree metaphor is replete with profound and powerful symbolism. It is known that from the American Revolution onwards, trees began to symbolise resistance and revolution. The practice first emerged in Boston in 1765, when an elm tree, known as the Liberty Tree, became the focal point of resistance against the Stamp Act. Although the concept was first established in the United States, it was the French Revolution that led to its dissemination on a broader scale. This was largely due to the efforts of Norbert Pressac, who is credited with planting the first symbolic tree in France in 1790. This practice was established in the patriotic spirit when the French Convention consolidated its importance by issuing a decree to ensure that a tree of liberty was planted and maintained in every commune, as a symbol of the principles of 'liberté, égalité, fraternité' (Mancuso 2020: 24–25).

This metaphor is thus a powerful revolutionary symbol, and the association between OS and the tree evokes a shared heritage, but also a radical and systemic change. Eva Méndez's Christmas tree also reflects and reveals this spirit of transformative change, embodied by the process of reforming research assessment.

4. *The Forest of OS. Towards an Ecological Intelligence*

This vision of a complex, living network serves as the perfect bridge to my proposal to represent OS with a new metaphor—that of the forest—which offers a synthesis that incorporates the strengths of the previous images and metaphors. The forest is, in fact, a natural organism like the mushroom and the tree, and its revolutionary roots evoke the symbolism of the latter¹³. It encompasses the view of knowledge as a continuous living process, symbolised by the wheel, and its vast system of interconnected roots functions as a graph, sharing the distributed topology while adding a vegetal and ecological intelligence.

In a forest or woodland, the trees that form part of it are not separated from one another; through their roots, they form an underground network that unites them all into a single, widespread network. Plants exchange knowledge as a natural commons¹⁴, based on an open infrastructure (provided by the root system but also by the canopies and other communication channels activated within it). The infrastructure functions like a circulatory system (which lacks a command centre) and enables the transport of fluids from the bottom upwards (xylem) and vice versa (phloem). Plants, however, have various systems (hydraulic, electrical, chemical-hormonal) for transmitting information, for example regarding the presence or absence of water. Unlike in animals, these systems are complementary and do not have a single data processing centre: plants can communicate from the roots to the canopy and vice versa, but also between leaves and through the roots. Plants possess distributed intelligence, so information chooses the best route according to need.

¹³ The 1848 map of the 'trees of fraternity', discovered by Mancuso (2020: 17–41), depicts a map and a plan of the world in which places are connected by common roots, an underground root system that represents on paper the network of root networks uniting the trees of the forest. Mancuso has verified the reliability of the data on the 1848 map, noting that the thickness of the roots linking the various locations was greater the more 'trees of liberty' there were in a region. When viewed in its entirety, the map forms an enormous poplar tree – from the Latin name for poplar, *populus* – a tribute to the peoples who embraced the revolution. As Ramazan Turgut observed during the seminar "Images of Open Science", organised with Cristina Marras in Rome in September 2025, the value of brotherhood is also associated with the forest in a poem by the poet Nazim Hikmet, which reads: "To live! Like a single, free tree, Live! Like a forest in brotherhood/sisterhood!" – in Turkish: *Yasamak bir ağaç gibi, tek ve hür, Ve bir orman gibi kardeşesine*.

¹⁴ See Albagli et al. 2019, in which the authors critically analyse Elinor Ostrom's IAD (Institutional Analysis and Development) framework (Hess, Ostrom 2007), which they apply to an open science action-research project in Ubatuba, Brazil. The authors examine how local communities manage natural and knowledge commons, moving beyond the traditional view that sees them as separate entities. Through the study of political and territorial tensions, the article highlights that knowledge production and the protection of physical resources are interconnected dimensions of a single process of 'commoning'. The research also suggests that mere access to information is not sufficient to resolve power asymmetries, necessitating a form of knowledge that incorporates the experiential knowledge of local populations. In conclusion, Ostrom's contribution is supplemented by perspectives that place greater emphasis on social conflicts and the historical dynamics of territories.

A salient feature of the forest is the presence of extensive, interconnected communities that facilitate the exchange of nutrients, water, and information via their root systems. These communities engage in communication and collaboration, fostering a relationship that is crucial for the forest's ecosystem. The model of mutual aid, in which the primary factors of evolution and survival are identified as solidarity and mutual support – that is, values associated with the principle of collaboration, rather than the notion of competition in the struggle for survival (Kropotkin 1902) – characterises this ecosystem. This symbol thus represents the value and benefits that a community of individuals can enjoy compared to being isolated, and which stem from collaboration between individuals as part of a community.

As a natural entity, the forest exists for its own sake not serving any particular purpose. It is composed of a diverse array of individuals, and within its ecosystem, the collective is greater than the sum of its constituent parts. Furthermore, the forest metaphor conveys the idea of a collective endeavour in which different individuals contribute to the health of the whole. Plants, in fact, communicate with one another through various senses and a language composed of chemical molecules released into the air or water. Another form of communication is gestural, such as fleeing from the shade or the shyness of the foliage. Plant physiologists have shown how some families avoid contact with others, and that plants recognise relatives; that is, they can identify individuals with whom they share strong genetic similarities in order to defend their own genetic heritage, with whom they share roots to develop further outwards, in a non-competitive activity linked to genetic proximity. Not all interactions are peaceful, so the plant will try to understand and behave accordingly. Studies show that there are species that are more or less competitive, aggressive or collaborative, in a manner similar to the animal world from a behavioural perspective. However, the forest model is more collaborative than the animal one. Indeed, a forest can be conceptualised as a super-organism, a term coined to denote an entity that exists as a result of the interaction between the constituent trees (Mancuso 2013). Plants in a forest possess a swarm intelligence that allows them to behave as a multitude (like a colony of ants, or a school of fish, or a flock of birds). If the plant is a swarm, the forest is a swarm of swarms (Mancuso 2013: 124). In the forest of OS, the invisible work of maintenance, care and community-building is the glue that binds the individual researchers, communities and institutions, making the whole greater than the sum of its parts.

Several decades of discoveries have shed light on the fact that plants are not passive; rather, they are intelligent and capable of communicating with one another and with other species. As has been demonstrated, the arguments used to deny that plants are intelligent are based on prejudice (Darwin 1908). Conversely, plants have a modular body (lacking individual organs); they are divisible beings equipped with numerous control centres, with a network structure similar to the Internet; they are sentient (in addition to our five senses, they possess at least fifteen others); and they are brilliant in the choices they make to survive (Mancuso 2013). The metaphor of the forest thus evokes a living ecosystem that is based on common infrastructures, collaborative, biodiverse, inclusive, and highly intelligent – in other words, of great quality.

The image below offers a snapshot of a subset of the forest. The various individuals, projects, laboratories and groups that form part of the scientific ecosystem reflect its biodiversity. The forest image is also available in a blank version and can be populated as desired¹⁵.

Fig. 11 – The Forest of Open Science (Di Donato 2026).

The roots of the forest are of particular importance, as they facilitate connection between trees and the elements of the rhizosphere, defined as the portion of soil with which they are in contact and which serves as a habitat for a diverse array of organisms, including microorganisms, mushrooms, insects and bacteria. These organisms collectively form an ecological niche that is characterised by a state of balance, maintained through collaborative interaction and communication with the plants. These are examples of a mutualistic symbiotic association, in which all organisms are said to benefit (Mancuso 2013:84). In a similar manner, the existence of a public and open infrastructure (comprising universities, research bodies, scientific institutions and associations, as well as digital infrastructures, with the European Open Science Cloud being of particular significance in the European context) functions as a complex distributed system that enables and promotes the exchange and sharing of knowledge. The principles of ethical research, which uphold and apply professional ethics and standards as a guarantee of the very quality of research and of trust in the

¹⁵ The drawing of the forest with the practices, the empty forest and an editable list of labels can be found in Di Donato (2026). These tools can be used in teaching activities and as a means for self-reflection.

reputation and public image of science, are another element of fundamental importance, on a par with tools and practices for responsible research evaluation—that is, evaluation that is transparent, inclusive and of high quality. The aforementioned elements, as evoked in Méndez’s mushroom and Christmas tree, in Figure 11 are complemented by multilingualism. The existence of a multitude of languages reflects a plurality of cultures, thus giving rise to the emergence of pluralistic views (Marras 2021). This phenomenon constitutes a fundamental aspect of OS.

The individual trees (whether projects, groups or individuals) embody different practices, linked to their own context, research needs and available resources. Figure 11 represents this biodiversity both graphically, where the trees differ in species, colour and size, and through the labels, which indicate the specific practices or activities that characterise them. As an example, the yellow poplar in the centre, characterised by deep roots can represent a French community that practises open access, releases open data, and uses or produces open hardware. In this ecosystem, each contributes in its own way and according to its needs; for example, dead trees (completed projects or disused datasets) continue to provide nourishment and structure, performing a vital function.

The tree trunks define the various legal and regulatory contexts, local policies, the adoption of specific recommendations (such as the CoARA commitments) or copyleft licences, which enable the reuse of knowledge, and carry sap to the branches and leaves. In the image, the term ‘law’ is translated into different languages (e.g. derecho, diritto, droit, Rechts) to convey the diversity of the national contexts in which the individuals, groups, labs or projects operate. Its shared legal basis defines OS as a democracy and as a *res publica*, which shares ethical and scientific standards and is founded on a cosmopolitan ideal (Di Donato 2011).

When juxtaposed with the image of a solitary tree, the forest evokes a more complex concept, one that encompasses the intricate relationships between individuals, as well as the dynamic interplay between the internal and the external. The image is thus enriched by aggregators (e.g. wind, bees, birds and mushrooms) and resources (i.e. earth, light and water).

As Sepehri (2025) points out, the forest metaphor also represents various forms of inequality resulting from asymmetries and injustices, thereby enabling strong parallels with the systemic challenges facing the OS movement:

- **Unequal Resource Distribution:** In a real forest, tall canopy trees monopolize sunlight, often starving the understory plants below. Root systems compete fiercely for water and nutrients. This directly mirrors how privileged institutions and Anglophone-centric research dominate the global knowledge landscape, capturing the majority of visibility, funding, and resources.
- **Absence of Equal Opportunity:** A seed’s survival is heavily dependent on the chance of where it lands. A spot with fertile soil and adequate light allows it to thrive, while an equally viable seed may perish in deep shade. This reflects the systemic barriers and positional advantages in academia, where success is often contingent on pedigree and geography rather than merit alone.
- **Exclusion and Competition:** Some plant species engage in allelopathy, releasing chemicals to actively suppress the growth of competitors. This is a stark metaphor for the persistent competition for funding and recognition, the gatekeeping practices of established journals, and the institutional rivalries that can stifle collaboration.
- **Efficiency Without Fairness:** A forest is a remarkably resilient and efficient system, but its efficiency is achieved through brutal cycles of dominance, decay, and regrowth. It is a system of winners and losers. This parallels how the current scientific ecosystem can be highly efficient at producing a massive volume of outputs while failing to be fair or equitable in its methods of evaluation and reward. (Sepehri 2025)

The power of the forest metaphor, therefore, lies both in its ability to make real tensions visible, forcing us to confront the gap between the model and our practices, and in its capacity to define a model of OS grounded in ecological intelligence - based on biodiversity and inclusion, collaboration, and quality. The forest thus serves as a descriptive model, urging us to confront the real disparities in our knowledge ecosystems, while also helping us define a vision, a philosophical framework for understanding where we are and where we want to go.

In a recent study, Sabina Leonelli explored a specific reconceptualisation of the potential and purposes of digital technology and related forms of algorithmic rationality. In doing so, she revisited the philosophical basis of Environmental Intelligence (EI) (Leonelli, 2025). Whilst the term is most often associated with endeavours to utilise data science and AI to address climate change, with a strong emphasis on the problem-solving capabilities of coding and associated digital technologies, Leonelli proposes its utilisation as a philosophical framing for the role played by computational skills and technologies in supporting interactions between humans and their environments. This includes human and non-human life, along with its habitats and artificial creations. Leonelli's reflection starts from six considerations pertaining to the nature of intelligence and a situated more-than-human view of intelligence, the role of humans and research in the environment and the significance of equity and diversity in the development and use of computational tools. According to her vision, "intelligence could be defined as the capacity of individuals and groups to respond and adapt to their environments" (Leonelli 2025: 5).

This definition is not dissimilar to the conception of intelligence "as the capacity to solve problems" - a faculty which is not exclusive to humans but is also exhibited by plants, which are regarded as sentient organisms capable of communication, social interaction and problem-solving through strategies that can be characterised as 'intelligent' (Mancuso, 2013).

The forest metaphor grounds OS in the vision of a vegetal (Mancuso, 2013) and environmental intelligence (Leonelli, 2025), which can be defined as an ecological and systemic vision of OS - that is biodiverse, inclusive, collaborative, collective and brilliant. Adopting such a perspective also implies the revision of conventional evaluation parameters. Rather than interrogating the innovation, efficiency or excellence of research, it becomes imperative to inquire into its role and behaviour within its ecosystem, by asking: How does it operate within it? How does it draw nourishment? How does it fertilize others? Is it sustainable, fair, inclusive? Is it creative, is it alive? (Mounier, 2022) And what concept of the common good does it address? (Leonelli, Rimini, 2026). The serious consideration of these questions has the effect of broadening our perspective to encompass not only the forest as a model, but also its capacity to serve as a representation of the enduring tensions and inequalities that are embedded within our knowledge ecosystems.

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Joint Research Unit¹⁶. The objective of the meeting was twofold: firstly, to discuss my ongoing work on a book about OS, which is due to be published by CNR Edizioni by the end of 2026; and secondly, to outline a methodology that would facilitate ongoing discussion of research projects and publications. The organisation of both seminars as invitational events with limited places was deliberate, with the objective being to facilitate exchange, sharing and group work. Furthermore, this approach was taken to ensure the participation of individuals from diverse backgrounds, as well as those with expertise and knowledge of OS.

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Fig. 12. The participants to the Seminar “Le immagini della scienza aperta”, 24 September 2025. Photo by Silvestro Caligiuri.

¹⁶ The results will be published in the form of a multimedia product.

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